

MUTUAL COAGULATION OF COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS. INTERACTION OF COPPER FERROCYANIDE WITH FERRIC HYDROXIDE, THORIUM HYDROXIDE AND CERIC HYDROXIDE.

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Mutual coagulation of the pairs copper ferrocyanide and ferric hydroxide, copper ferrocyanide and thorium hydroxide and copper ferrocyanide and ceric hydroxide has been studied. It is observed that the width of the zone of mutual coagulation is minimum when the charge on the colloidal particles of the reacting sols is maximum, the value of the minimum width also depending upon the hydration of the particles. The width of the zone of mutual coagulation seems to be mainly controlled by the charge on the colloidal particles, the fact whether the peptising electrolytes and other impurities present in the sols chemically react or not on mixing them being unimportant.

In previous papers (Barve, Paranjpe and Desai, *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1937, **6**, *ii*, 50; 1939, **8**, *ii*, 134), it has been shown that in the case of mutual coagulation of Prussian blue and (a) ferric hydroxide, (b) thorium hydroxide and (c) ceric hydroxide with the progress of dialysis, the width of the zone of mutual coagulation first decreases and then increases, the charge on the particles of the sols in all the cases first increasing and then decreasing at the same time. The sols tried so far were all acidic and the peptising electrolytes in them were such that on mixing the sols no chemical interaction took place. In the present case copper ferrocyanide has been substituted for Prussian blue as the former is basic, while the other sols have been kept the same, in order to study the effect of chemical interaction between the stabilising ions and to see if the same relation between the width of the zone of mutual coagulation and the charge on the colloidal particles of the sols as observed before holds good.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Copper ferrocyanide sol was prepared in the same manner as done by Chaudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 431) and ferric hydroxide, thorium hydroxide and ceric hydroxide as done by Desai and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). Details of dialysis and charge measurements were the same as given in earlier papers.

* The experimental work has been carried out entirely by Mr. V. C. Vora under the direction of the other two authors.

The zone of mutual coagulation was first determined roughly by finding out in each case the amounts of the two reacting sols at which turbidity first appears and then disappears, the total volume of the mixture being kept 10 c.c. The zone of complete coagulation was afterwards accurately determined by taking a number of mixtures in the boundary region of the zone previously roughly determined, by varying the amount of the colloids by 0.05 c.c. The mixtures were then centrifuged for 3 minutes at about 2500 r.p.m. and examined for complete coagulation. When the presence of a small amount of colloid was not readily determined in the supernatant liquid by visual observation, the latter was pipetted off and treated with an excess of suitable electrolyte solutions. The absence of any turbidity on standing was taken as an indication that no colloid was present in the supernatant liquid.

The results of charge measurements are given in Table I and those of the determination of the zone of mutual coagulation in Tables II-IV.

TABLE I.

Cathaphoretic speed $\times 10^5$.

Dialysed for	Copper ferrocyanide.	Ferric hydroxide.	Thorium hydroxide.	Ceric hydroxide.
0 days	16.9	26.3	28.9	14.3
3	—	36.1	34.0	—
4	22.6	—	—	18.1
7	—	47.6	38.1	—
8	29.4	—	—	26.4
11	—	63.4	41.3	—
12	38.5	—	—	33.6
14	—	78.8	42.6	—
15	46.2	—	—	42.9
18	—	41.9	32.4	—
19	34.2	—	—	33.2
22	—	29.3	27.5	—
23	23.7	—	—	21.7

TABLE II.

Mutual coagulation of copper ferrocyanide by ferric hydroxide.

Numbers in different columns refer to c.c. of ferric hydroxide in 10 c.c. of the mixture of copper ferrocyanide and ferric hydroxide. A = Appearance of turbidity. Z = Zone of coagulation. D = Disappearance of turbidity.

Days of dialysis of copper ferrocyanide.

	0		3		7		11		14		18		22								
	A.	Z.																			
0	0.6	8.4	9.0	0.7	7.0	7.7	1.0	5.8	6.8	1.2	3.2	4.4	1.7	2.1	3.8	1.4	2.9	4.3	0.9	3.5	4.4
3	0.8	8.2	9.0	0.9	6.5	7.4	1.1	5.2	6.3	1.3	2.9	4.2	1.9	1.7	3.6	1.3	3.4	4.7	0.8	4.1	4.9
7	0.9	8.4	9.3	1.0	6.1	7.1	1.3	4.7	6.0	1.1	2.6	3.7	2.1	1.6	3.7	1.1	3.9	5.0	0.8	4.8	5.6
11	0.7	8.5	9.2	0.6	6.8	7.4	1.2	4.9	6.1	0.9	2.0	2.9	2.4	1.5	3.9	0.9	4.4	5.3	0.6	5.4	6.0
14	1.0	8.6	9.6	0.8	6.9	7.7	1.0	5.3	6.3	1.0	2.9	3.9	2.6	1.4	3.0	0.7	4.5	5.2	0.5	5.9	6.4
18	1.1	8.7	9.6	0.9	7.1	8.0	0.8	5.7	6.5	1.4	3.1	4.5	1.8	3.1	4.9	0.8	4.8	5.6	0.7	6.5	7.2
22	0.9	8.9	9.8	0.7	7.4	8.1	0.9	6.0	6.9	1.3	3.8	5.1	1.3	4.7	5.0	0.9	5.3	6.2	0.9	6.9	7.8

Days of dialysis of ferric hydroxide.

TABLE III.

Mutual coagulation of copper ferrocyanide by thorium hydroxide.

Numbers in different columns refer to c.c. of thorium hydroxide in 10 c.c. of the mixture of copper ferrocyanide and thorium hydroxide.

Days of dialysis of copper ferrocyanide.

	0		3		7		11		14		18		22								
	A.	Z. D.	A.	Z. D.	A.	Z. D.	A.	Z. D.	A.	Z. D.	A.	Z. D.	A.	Z. D.							
0	1.2	<u>6.6</u>	1.1	6.3	7.4	1.3	4.7	6.0	0.9	3.1	4.0	1.0	2.6	3.6	1.2	3.6	4.8	0.9	4.1	5.0	
3	1.4	6.9	8.3	1.4	<u>5.6</u>	7.0	1.2	3.9	5.1	0.8	3.5	4.3	1.3	2.8	4.1	1.1	3.8	4.9	0.8	4.3	5.1
7	1.3	7.1	8.4	1.2	4.8	6.0	1.1	<u>4.9</u>	6.0	1.1	3.0	4.1	1.6	2.4	4.0	0.9	4.3	5.2	0.6	4.8	5.4
11	1.0	7.8	8.8	1.3	5.4	6.7	1.0	5.1	6.1	1.6	<u>3.2</u>	4.8	1.8	2.3	4.1	0.7	4.8	5.5	0.7	5.1	5.8
14	1.5	8.0	9.5	1.4	5.9	7.3	0.9	5.4	6.3	1.4	<u>3.6</u>	5.0	2.2	1.9	4.1	0.9	5.0	5.9	0.9	5.5	6.4
18	1.3	8.2	9.5	1.2	6.7	7.9	0.8	6.0	6.8	1.2	3.9	5.1	1.6	2.6	4.2	1.3	<u>4.2</u>	5.5	1.1	5.9	7.0
22	1.2	8.5	9.7	1.0	6.9	7.9	0.7	6.3	7.0	0.9	<u>4.6</u>	5.5	1.1	3.7	4.8	1.2	4.1	5.3	1.0	<u>6.2</u>	7.2

Days of dialysis of thorium hydroxide

TABLE IV.

Mutual coagulation of copper ferrocyanide by ceric hydroxide.

Numbers in different columns refer to c.c. of ceric hydroxide in 10 c.c. of the mixture of copper ferrocyanide and ceric hydroxide.

Days of dialysis of copper ferrocyanide.

	0		4		8		12		15		19		23								
	A.	Z.																			
0	1.4	8.0	9.4	1.2	7.5	8.7	1.1	6.5	7.6	1.6	5.8	7.4	1.4	5.1	6.5	1.1	6.1	7.2	0.9	7.4	8.3
4	1.3	8.2	9.5	1.0	7.1	8.1	1.6	6.6	8.2	1.4	6.0	7.4	1.2	5.6	6.8	1.0	6.3	7.3	0.8	7.6	8.4
8	1.6	8.0	9.6	1.3	7.4	8.7	2.0	6.7	8.7	1.5	6.2	7.7	1.8	5.0	6.8	0.8	6.7	7.5	1.0	7.8	8.8
12	1.4	8.3	9.7	1.2	7.3	8.5	1.8	6.4	8.2	1.3	6.5	7.8	2.2	4.9	7.1	0.9	7.1	8.0	0.7	8.0	8.7
15	1.3	8.4	9.7	1.0	7.8	8.8	1.4	6.1	7.5	1.2	5.9	7.1	2.8	4.2	7.0	1.3	6.4	7.7	0.9	8.1	9.0
19	1.2	8.6	9.8	1.2	8.0	9.2	1.0	6.8	7.8	1.1	5.6	6.7	2.0	4.8	6.8	1.4	6.8	8.2	1.0	8.0	9.0
23	1.2	8.7	9.8	1.1	8.3	9.4	1.1	6.9	8.0	1.0	5.4	6.4	1.3	5.8	7.1	1.0	7.0	8.0	0.9	8.2	9.1

Days of dialysis of ceric hydroxide

DISCUSSION.

From Table I it will appear that in all the cases with the progress of dialysis, the cataphoretic speed, *i.e.* the charge on the colloidal particles, first increases, reaches a maximum and then decreases. The initial increase in cataphoretic speed is due to some of the oppositely charged ions which are bound with the primarily adsorbed, *i.e.* preferentially adsorbed similarly charged ions, as a result of electrical attraction, becoming free as their concentration in the sol diminishes during dialysis; the final decrease in cataphoretic speed is due to desorption of the preferentially adsorbed similarly charged ions from the surface of the particles, *i.e.* from the inner sheet of the double layer as their concentration in the intermicellary liquid becomes very low in the latter stages of dialysis (Desai, Barve and Paranjpe, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1939, 59, 22).

It will appear from Tables II, III and IV that when to one of the sols dialysed for a certain period, another sol dialysed for different periods is added, the changes in the range (value of Z) within which mutual coagulation takes place are not regular. This is to be expected as sols dialysed for different periods contain different amounts of impurities and they will change the charge on the particles differently on mixing.

If we consider the range within which mutual coagulation occurs for both the sols dialysed for the same periods, it appears that with the progress of dialysis, it (value of Z underlined in Tables II, III and IV) first decreases, reaches a minimum value and then increases. For the pairs copper ferrocyanide and ferric hydroxide, copper ferrocyanide and thorium hydroxide and copper ferrocyanide and ceric hydroxide, the smallest value of the width of the zone of mutual coagulation has been 1.4, 1.9 and 4.2 units respectively occurring for sols dialysed for 14 to 15 days. From Table I it is seen that the maximum value of charge has also occurred for sols dialysed for about the same period. It is thus clear that even when the two reacting sols contain peptising electrolytes and other impurities, which may chemically react on mixing them, the width of the zone of mutual coagulation is mainly controlled by charge on the particles of the sols. When the charge on the particles of one of the sols, which is in excess, is highest, the amount of the other oppositely charged colloid required to be added to coagulate it, will have to be sufficiently large so as to lower down the charge to such a value that aggregation can take place, producing turbidity; similarly the disappearance of turbidity or its appearance from the other end (*i.e.* when the second colloid is in excess and its particles have the highest charge) will

occur only when large amount of the coagulating colloid from that end is added. Thus the zone of precipitation will be the narrowest, *i.e.*, the value of Z will be the smallest when the particles of both the sols have greatest charge.

As mentioned before, the smallest value of the width of the zone of mutual coagulation has been 1.4, 1.9 and 4.2 in the case of the pairs copper ferrocyanide and (a) ferric hydroxide, (b) thorium hydroxide and (c) ceric hydroxide respectively. This difference in the values is probably due to a difference in hydration of the colloid particles of the three sols, the ceric hydroxide particles being decidedly more hydrated than those of ferric hydroxide or thorium hydroxide. This effect of hydration of the colloid particles has also been noticed in the case of other sols studied in this laboratory (Barve, Vora and Desai, *loc. cit.*).

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